

athena

gender equality to unlock
research potential

D7.2 Project visual identity and website

Acronym: ATHENA

Title: Implementing gender equality plans to unlock research potential of RPOs and RFOs in Europe

Grant Agreement n° 101006416

CONSULTA EUROPA
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Jožef Stefan Institute, Ljubljana, Slovenia

Uniwersytet
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Universidad de
Las Palmas de
Gran Canaria

ENR
COMPAGNIE NATIONALE DU RHÔNE

INSTITUTE FOR
RESEARCH IN SOCIAL
COMMUNICATION SAS

UNIVERSITY OF RUSE
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Gobierno de Canarias
Consejería de Economía,
Conocimiento y Empleo
Agencia Canaria de Investigación,
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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101006416

Version history

Version	Date	Comments / Changes	Author/ Reviewer
0.1	23/07/2021	1st draft version sent to Steering Committee for comments	Carolina Bettencourt Gisela Nascimento
1.0	27/07/2021	2nd draft version with SC comments	Steering Committee

Document Information

Project Acronym	ATHENA
Project Title	Implementing gender equality plans to unlock research potential of RPOs and RFOs in Europe
Project Number	101006416
Instrument	CSA - Coordination and support action
Topic	SwafS-09-2018-2019-2020 - Supporting research organisations to implement gender equality plans
Project Start Date	01/02/2021
Project Duration	48 months
Work Package	WP7 Dissemination and communication
Task	Task 7.2 Project visual identity and promotional materials and Task 7.3 Project website, social media and newsletter
Deliverable	D7.2 Project visual identity and website
Due Date	30/06/2021
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Dissemination Level ¹	PU
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Version	1.0
Status	Final
Author (s)	Carolina Bettencourt, Gisela Nascimento, Luz Paramio
Reviewers	Steering Committee

¹ PU= Public, CO=Confidential, only for members of the Consortium (including the Commission Services), CL=Classified, as referred in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

WP	Work package
D	Deliverable
CSA	Coordination and support action
RFO	Research Funding Organisation
RPO	Research Performing Organisation
GEP	Gender Equality Plan
PU	Public

1. Introduction

This report summarizes the elements of the visual identity of the ATHENA project and the structure of the website and it is divided into three main categories: Introduction, Project Visual Identity and Website.

The objective of the project visual identity is to ensure a coherent and harmonized recognition of the project. In this way, the following material has been produced during the first phase of the ATHENA project. The goals of the dissemination materials are to create awareness about the project and its specific area of work, promote the project results to the different defined target groups and to address the widest possible audience.

The website will be an important communication channel to promote the project and its objectives and update interested parties on progress, results and outcomes.

2. Project visual identity

The project visual identity includes the layout of promotional material such as logo, flyers, brochures, posters, roll-up, banner, power point presentation, word template and newsletter, etc. All promotional materials will be published in English and translated by the partners in their respective languages (Bulgarian, Croatian, Czech, Italian, Polish, Portuguese, Romanian, Slovenian, Slovak and Spanish).

2.1 Logotype

The logotype will be used during the whole life of the project in all communication and dissemination materials.

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Figure 1- ATHENA logotype (colour version)

2.1.1 Concept

For the development of the logotype, a contest in the ATHENA universities was launched among students and professors that were asked to provide insights and/or examples of the project logo. The overall objective of the logo contest was to engage and create awareness to the students of the gender issues in science and its constraints in research careers.

The logo chosen to identify the ATHENA project reflects some of the aspects linked to the concept of equality between women and men, a fundamental value of the European Union and vital to its economic and social development. It is represented in this case by various elements related to the thematic, such as a woman silhouette, gender symbols for male and female and research environment. All these elements have been arranged in a dynamic set that conveys the project concept.

2.1.2 Guidelines for graphic identity

According to the guidelines of the ATHENA logo competition, the chosen logo proposal is aligned with the project thematic. The image has aesthetic quality and is stimulating, motivating and effective in communicating the phenomenon or concept of gender equality.

2.1.3 Construction and proportions

Figure 2- ATHENA logotype (construction and proportions)

2.1.4 Chromatic composition

Figure 3- ATHENA logotype (chromatic composition)

2.1.5 Not allowed uses

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Do not change the colour.

Do not alter the proportions.

Figure 4- ATHENA logotype (not allowed uses examples)

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2.1.6 Examples of logo application

Figure 5 - ATHENA logotype (examples of logo application)

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2.1.7 ATHENA Typography

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Figure 6- ATHENA Typography

2.2 ATHENA documents templates

2.2.1 Word document

Figure 7- ATHENA Word document template

2.2.2 PowerPoint presentation

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Title Example replace it

A SUBTITLE CAN BE ADDED

athenaequality.eu

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101006416

Short Title

— Bigger Title or description...

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Short Title

— Thank you for your attention!

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101006416

Figure 8- ATHENA Powerpoint template

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2.2.3 Flyer

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Figure 9- ATHENA flyer templates

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2.2.4 Brochure

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GENDER EQUALITY TO UNLOCK RESEARCH POTENTIAL

athenaequality.eu

#GENDEREQUALITY2021

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Figure 10- ATHENA brochure templates

2.2.5 Poster

Figure 11- ATHENA poster templates

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2.2.6 Roll-up

Figure 12- ATHENA roll-up templates

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2.2.7 Newsletter

ISSUE
01
July 2021

Monthly Newsletter

IN THIS ISSUE

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NEWSLETTER ISSUE 01 | PAGE 1/4

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NEWSLETTER ISSUE 01 | PAGE 4/4

Figure 13- ATHENA newsletter templates

3. Website

The dedicated ATHENA project website – www.athenaequality.eu plays multiple roles:

- An important communication channel providing information on the development and implementation of GEPs in research organizations;
- A communication resource to provide standard project information covering objectives, partners, work packages, progress and results;
- A repository to update information about the gender equality audit carried out under WP2 on provisions regulations and laws gender equality existing in partner countries;
- A group of links to other EU-funded projects focusing on gender equality issues and to the social media pages of the project;
- A resource to integrate the ATHENA e-Platform for Action developed under WP6.

The public project website is visually attractive and informative to facilitate continuous project partner communication. New visual media and dynamic outreach products are and will be used on the website.

3.1 Key features

Key features of the website include:

Home

- Images & synthetic phrase of the Athena Project; Grant Agreement number and funding; links to social media pages of the project, including also news; newsletters and events
- Section to subscribe the Athena newsletters.

About Athena

- Mini-description of the Athena Project and representative images; main objective (Implementation of GEPs in research organizations) and project factsheet
- Work Packages (WP1-WP7 with description available)
- Advisory Board (photos and description)
- Partners (logos and description)
- Other Collaborations and sister projects

Progress & Results

- Gender Equality Plans
- Webinars & Workshops

- Main Deliverables
- Publications
- ATHENA Dissemination Materials
- ATHENA Calendar

ATHENA e-Platform for Action

To be developed by WP6 Sustainability strategy to ensure replication of GEPs and project results

News & Events

- News
- Newsletters
- Events

Contact

(Address, telephone and e-mail)

3.2 Content tree

Figure 14- Website content tree

3.3 List of web images captures

4.3.1 Front / Landing page (Home)

Figure 15- Front / Landing page (Home)

4.3.2 About ATHENA

The screenshot shows the ATHENA website interface. At the top, there is a navigation menu with links: Home, About ATHENA, Progress & Results, ATHENA a Platform for Action, News & Events, and Contact. The main content area features a large image of a woman in a lab coat using a microscope. To the left of this image, the text reads: "ONE OF THE MAIN OBJECTIVES OF EUROPE'S SOCIETIES IS THE ELIMINATION OF ALL TYPES OF DISCRIMINATION ASSOCIATED WITH GENDER." Below this, a paragraph explains that despite a high number of highly skilled female graduates, few are embracing a research career, and that ATHENA aims to address these issues through Gender Equality Plans (GEPs) in 6 Research Performing and 2 Research Funding organisations. To the right of the main text, there is a detailed paragraph about the implementation of GEPs, mentioning a participatory process and the goal of improving research performance. At the bottom of the page, there is a section titled "Implementation of GEPs in research organisations" with an illustration of people working together around a table with charts and documents.

Figure 16- About ATHENA

4.3.3 Progress & Results

Figure 17- Progress & Results

4.3.5 News & Events

The screenshot displays the Athena website's News & Events page. At the top, there is a navigation bar with links for Home, About Athena, Progress & Results, ATHENA e-Platform for Action, News & Events, and Contact. The main content is divided into three sections:

- News:** This section features three news items. The first item is titled "ATHENA final logo inspired by the insights of a student of the Angel Kanchev University of Ruse, Bulgaria" and is dated July 19, 2021. The second item is titled "Sed consectetur ornare iaculis. Curabitur pulvinar ultricies nulla id ultrices. Nunc at massa non nunc ..." and is dated May 20, 2021. The third item is titled "Aenean pulvinar dui vehicula nisi pellentesque porttitor. Proin non semper risus. Nullam mattis mauris ..." and is dated January 17, 2021. A "View All" button is located below these items.
- Newsletters:** This section features a featured issue titled "Monthly Newsletter" for July 2021, labeled as "ISSUE 01". To the right, there is a section titled "IN THIS ISSUE" with a list of six items, each with a brief description and a date. A "Read" button is located below the featured issue.
- Events:** This section features three event items. The first item is titled "In quis dui at quam blandit convallis." and is dated July 19, 2021. The second item is titled "Sed consectetur ornare iaculis." and is dated May 20, 2021. The third item is titled "Curabitur pulvinar ultricies nulla id ultrices." and is dated January 17, 2021. A "View All" button is located below these items.

Figure 18- News & Events

3.4 Technical specifications

The website of the Athena project (www.athenaequality.eu) is developed with a content manager, or better known as CMS. Wordpress was chosen for this development due to its ease of management and use, as well for the huge community that supports it.

It was designed using responsive design so it can adapt properly to any device (mobile, tablet or desktop). It's compatible with the recent versions of the most used browsers available.

3.5 Development timeline

- **July 22, 2021** - Delivery and validation of designs: Front/Landing (Home), About ATHENA, Progress & Results, ATHENA e-Platform for Action, News & Events

- **August, 2021** - Development of the ATHENA website: Front/Landing (Home), About ATHENA, Progress & Results, ATHENA e-Platform for Action, News & Events